

THE ORIGINALITY OF TEACHING DISCIPLINE "RUSSIAN LANGUAGE AND CULTURE OF SPEECH" IN THE AGRICULTURAL UNIVERSITY

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the study of the features of teaching the discipline "Russian language and culture of speech" in an agricultural university. The main conclusion of this study is that the study of the discipline "Russian language and culture of speech" in an agricultural university is an important stage in the education of a modern specialist.

Key words: project activity, role play, traditional forms of work, teaching methods.

In modern times, in which processes of integration and globalization are taking place, higher education cannot be faced with the task of training only a narrow specialist. A graduate of a higher education institution must possess many skills in order to be competitive in the labor market, including speaking and writing skills in a professional field; literate writing and speaking skills.

The demand for competent specialists is dictated by time. In the context of the widespread dissemination of colloquial speech, negative trends appear: grammatical errors are fixed in the language as sample sentences, spelling errors, word usage is broken, stylistic boundaries are erased. Therefore, it is not superfluous for a good agronomist, engineer, livestock specialist, veterinarian to have a high level of speech culture, like any other specialist.

As a result of studying the course "Russian Language and Culture of Speech", the student should receive basic information about speech communication, about ways to organize effective speech communication. A student who has mastered the course must have the skills to improve his oral and written speech, especially in the professional field, know the criteria for assessing the correctness of speech, master the difficult norms of pronunciation, stress, grammar, and be able to produce professionally significant texts.

The curriculum of the discipline "Russian language and culture of speech" includes three main modules:

1. Culture of speech and norms of the Russian literary language.
2. The relevance of speech and the culture of speech production.
3. Culture of verbal communication.

The main attention in the study of the discipline is given to such important areas of speech communication as scientific and official business. Exercises and tasks are designed in such a way that they contain a lot of agricultural vocabulary. For example, tasks according to accentological norms: emphasize the words agroengineering, agronomy, veterinary medicine, combiner, beet, toothed, caterpillar and under. When studying the genres of official business style, the emphasis is on the preparation of documents necessary in the process of studying at a university, and then in work: a statement, contract, explanatory note, resume,

memorandum, business letter, etc. To achieve educational goals, both traditional forms of work and interactive methods are used during classes: role-playing game, project activity, learning in cooperation, etc. A roleplaying game is an interactive method that allows you to learn from your own experience through a specially organized and regulated living of a life and professional situation, turns learning into a creative laboratory of self-education, it is a speech, game and learning activity at the same time¹. The role-playing game allows students to apply the acquired knowledge to solve practical problems, increases their motivation.

Project activity belongs to the category of innovative, as it involves the transformation of reality, is based on the appropriate technology that can be unified, mastered and improved.

The purpose of the project activity is the understanding and application by students of the knowledge, skills and abilities acquired in the study of various subjects (on an integration basis).

The main idea of learning in cooperation is to create conditions for active joint learning activities of students in various learning situations.

How to arouse interest in the study of the discipline "Russian language and culture of speech" among students of an agricultural university? The answer is obvious: it is necessary to make the learning process bright, entertaining, informal.

Everyone knows that through the game a person in early childhood learns the world, because it is the game that activates the process of cognition of the surrounding reality, develops the creative abilities of the child, helps him to show his best sides in team work.

The game helps students to understand the processes taking place in the Russian language, remember the norms well and be able to apply them in practice, teaches them to analyze their speech and the speech of others, work with basic dictionaries that reflect the norms of the Russian literary language, expands the horizons and vocabulary of students. The game also carries a great emotional charge, forms such qualities of a creative person as initiative, determination, the ability to quickly find the right solution.

Thus, summing up, it should be noted that the study of the discipline "Russian language and culture of speech" in an agricultural university is an important stage in the education of a modern specialist. In order to make the learning process bright, entertaining, informal, it is necessary to use elements of gaming technologies in the work along with traditional classes.

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